

Special Relativity, Lagrangian Theory and Quantum Mechanics Part II

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. July 25, 2022

In Part I we suggested that free particle quantum mechanics seems to follow from special relativity. In this note, we focus on the idea of a rest frame defining a rest mass. In such a frame momentum is zero i.e. one has the 4-vector $(0, m_0) = (p, E)$. (x, t) , however, is also a 4-vector which is usually assigned to a point in space time. In Part I, however, we considered $(x, t) = (0, t_0)$ associating $p=0$ and $x=0$ and alternatively m_0 and t_0 . Velocity is usually defined as $dx/dt = v$, but using the Lorentz transformation (1) (with v set to $-v$), $(x, t) = (0, t_0)$ transforms to $x'/t' = v$. The relationship between x, p and t, E is further manifested through the Lorentz invariant $-Et + px$ in which E scales t and p, x . This we suggest breaks space into pieces proportional to $1/p$ and time (independently) into pieces proportional to $1/E$

We next consider particles "created" at different x points. In other words $(0, m_0)$ applies, but the particles are at different x positions. In order to keep the relationship $p=0, x=0$, one must have an x origin at all particle positions. Then spatial scaling of $1/p$ does not line up unless the particles are n/p (n =integer) apart. Otherwise the scaling in space is unaligned. For different p , scaling in space is unaligned already with $(0, m_0)$ and $(0, t_0)$. Thus for two particles with the same p , but created at different x values at different times and arriving at x_1, t_1 , if there is no alignment, special relativity suggests these two are distinguishable, while Newtonian mechanics does not distinguish. This distinguishability, however, depends on a physical mechanism i.e. a wavelength. Thus, even without considering different p (momentum) values, two identical momenta should be distinguishable if they are not aligned in terms of p scaling even for the same rest mass m_0 . This we argue is strictly a result of special relativity and is support for the $\exp(ipx)$ form of quantum free particle mechanics.

Special Relativity and x'/t'

Velocity in classical mechanics is defined as dx/dt . For a particle moving at a constant velocity $v=x/t$ if $x=0, t=0$ at the start. Interestingly in special relativity $x=0$ and $t=t_0$ transforms under a Lorentz transformation to $v = x'/t'$. In other words, in one frame the particle is not moving, but has $x=0$ and $t=t_0$, but in the moving frame it is seen to be moving with v with the sense that it started at the origin $x'=0, t'=0$ in this new frame. I.e. using the Lorentz transformation form from (1) and setting $v = -v$ one has, provided $t_0 > 0$:

$$x' = 1/\sqrt{1-vv} \quad v t_0 \quad \text{and} \quad t' = 1/\sqrt{1-vv} \quad t_0 \quad \text{with} \quad c=1 \quad ((1))$$

As noted in Part I, every momentum (and velocity) can be formed from transforming $(0, m_0)$ and $(x=0, t=t_0)$.

Thus the association of $p=0, x=0$ seems to be enough to give the particle the property $v=x'/t'$ in the new frame for any $t_0 > 0$.

Scaling

The Lorentz invariant form $-Et+px$ seems to mathematically indicate time is scaled by E and space x by p . We have already noted that m_0 and $t=t_0$ seem to have a special relationship and keep $-Et$ separate from px . Thus there is independent cycling in time of the order $1/E$ and in space of the order $1/p$. In other words space is broken into pieces proportional to $1/p$.

Multiple X Origins

An immediate interesting feature of $v=x'/t'$ with x' being a measure from the origin and t' from $t'=0$ is that for particles with the same m_0 and v , but located at different x there are multiple origins in the system. Thus for the idea of space being broken into equal segments proportional to $1/p$, there is already an issue (even without bringing in different momentum values). If a second origin is shifted from the first by a noninteger fraction of $1/p$, then the two "rulers" with spacings proportional to $1/p$ are unaligned. In other words, two particles with the same m_0 and v , but created at different x, t points such that they arrive at x_1, t_1 at the same time are not identical in special relativity if one takes scaling seriously. They are distinguishable. (At this point there is only the notion of a single momentum and no potential or force.) In Newtonian mechanics the two particles would be indistinguishable at x_1, t_1 . It is not that full history is kept of a particle traveling through space, rather it is a position along a wavelength proportional to $1/p$ and possible phase shifts due to disturbances which are important. Experimentally one would see "interference" of the two particles at x_1, t_1 . This suggests that the breaking of space into $1/p$ pieces is physical and is compatible with a periodic function $\exp(ipx)$ which maintains a constant modulus. This result as mentioned in other notes follows from $-Et+px=A$ if one creates an eigenvalue equation:

$$-i\hbar/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

The Case of the Photon

It is interesting to note that free motion quantum mechanics already appears in the case of a photon. The photon solution $E_0 \exp(-iEt+ipx)$ (and a similar expression for B the magnetic field) follows from Maxwell's classical electrodynamical equations. These equations, however, are compatible with special relativity, in fact Lorentz developed the Lorentz transformations from them. $-Et+px$ appears in the photon solution and is Lorentz invariant. The wave features are again associated with the scaling of time by E and space x by p . For example, $\exp(ipx)$ is all that is needed to solve the two slit interference or single slit diffraction problem. A photon has zero rest mass so the classical wave result $0 = -E dt + p dx$ follows, but it is $\exp(ipx)$ which describes spatial motion in a wave sense. Thus the photon seems to demonstrate that special relativity may perhaps be the driving force behind free quantum behaviour.

Different Momenta

In Part I we focused on the idea of different momenta and argued that each momentum-velocity pair for a fixed m_0 is linked to a $(0, m_0)$ and $(x=0, t=t_0)$ and a different frame moving with a constant $-v$. We argued that different px scaling resulted which must be manifested physically. Each momentum, however, may also be linked with different origins, so it is not just the case that one has $\exp(ipx)$, there may also be phase shifts for the same p .

Conclusion

In conclusion we examine the idea of different particle origins in space for the same p, v, m_0 . We consider special relativity as the source of free quantum behaviour which we argue follows from the scaling of t by E and x by p in the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ which is also the free particle action (relativistic and nonrelativistic). We consider $(p, E) = (0, m_0)$ as a special rest frame which we link to $(x=0, t=t_0)$. In other words m_0 and t_0 have a special relationship as do $p=0$ and $x=0$. A Lorentz transformation yields $v=x'/t'$, but this assumes that $p=0$ is associated with $x=0$. If one has particles at different locations, there are multiple origins. Px implies that space may be broken into pieces proportional to $1/p$. For different origins, the different "rulers" with $1/p$ proportional spacings may not be aligned. Thus for two particles with the same p, m_0 and v arising at different points and arriving at x_1, t_1 , there would be distinguishability in special relativity which does not exist in Newtonian mechanics. This is compatible with "interference" at such a point and helps to justify the form $\exp(ipx)$ which may be derived from using $A=-Et+px$ and creating an eigenvalue equation for p .

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lorentz_transformation